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“JUAN’S SLEEP AND MENTAL HEALTH”

Juan sleeps late at night
Works till dusk and dawn
His mental health takes a toll
Slow, Tired, and Sleepy
Juan needs energy

Stop, Breath, and Get Rest
Juan must do these things
So that his mental health
will be at its best
Sleep Juan Sleep

Juan gets a good sleep
mental health improves
Energy, Happy, and Alive
Now Juan values sleep
He is now on the move